

Synthesis of Lanthanum(III), Praseodymium(III), Neodymium(III), Samarium(III), Gadolinium(III), Dysprosium(III) and Ytterbium(III) Metal Picrates and their Spectral, Magnetic and Pharmacological Studies

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The lanthanone picrates [Ln(picrate)₃].xH₂O (where, Ln=La^{III}, Pr^{III}, Nd^{III}, Sm^{III}, Gd^{III}, Dy^{III} and Yb^{III}) prepared and characterised by elemental analysis, ICP atomic absorption spectrophotometer, combustion analysis, molar conductance and molecular weight determination, show that they are electrolytes and possess spin-free octahedral stereochemistry. The hydrated *f*-metal picrates show that (i) the phenoxy group of 2,4,6-trinitrophenol is involved in bonding with the metals, (ii) the water molecules in the hydrated metal picrates are coordinated and (iii) the NO₂ groups do not participate in bonding with the metal. The Pr, Nd and Sm picrates have also been screened on blood pressure of albino rats.

THE reaction of picric acid with metal hydroxide is the common route to obtain metal picrate¹. We can prepare the different lanthanone picrates from their carbonate/chloride salt with excess of dry picric acid/silver picrate.

Experimental

All the chemicals used were of BDH/Loba/Merck make. The solvents were purified and made anhydrous before use.

Preparation and analysis of the compounds :

La^{III}, Pr^{III}, Dy^{III} and Yb^{III} picrates were prepared by the reaction of their corresponding metal chloride and silver picrate in hot water. Silver chloride formed was then filtered out and the filtrate was concentrated and cooled. The resulting solid was washed with chloroform and recrystallised from methanol-water (1 : 1, v/v) and all were found tlc-pure.

Nd^{III}, Sm^{III} and Gd^{III} picrates were prepared from their metal carbonates with picric acid (8 : 1, w/w) in hot water solution. The unreacted metal carbonates were filtered out and the solution was concentrated. The resulting solid was recrystallised from methanol-water (1 : 1, v/v).

The metals were analysed by ICP atomic absorption spectrometer, H and C were estimated by combustion analysis and N by microanalysis. Electrical conductance was measured on a MC-1, Mark V instrument. Molecular weights were determined on a 301A vapour pressure osmometer. Magnetic measurement at room temperature (300 ± 1 K) was

carried out on a 155 magnetometer. Infrared spectra were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer spectrophotometer.

Results and Discussion

All the lanthanone metal picrates are insoluble in CCl₄, CHCl₃, benzene and petroleum ether, and are freely soluble in hot water, alcohol and acetone. Physical data of the compounds are recorded in Table 1. Molar conductance values of the compounds reveal 1 : 2 stoichiometry.

The values of magnetic moments for the Pr^{III}-picrate (3.62 B.M.) and Nd^{III}-picrate (3.52 B.M.) having ³H₄ and ⁴I_{9/2} ground state terms respectively, are close to those for complexed and free-ions as reported², suggesting octahedral crystal field around the metal ions. However, the value of 1.70 B.M. observed for the Sm^{III}-picrate (⁶H_{5/2} the ground state) against the calculated values of 0.84 B.M. suggests a considerable population of the excited (⁶H_{7/2}) *J* levels of the metal ions. In case of the Sm^{III}-picrates the observed values are almost double to the theoretical, which is justified by that the first emitted *J* state is very close to the ground state causing an increase³ in magnetic moment. The magnetic moment of the Dy^{III}, Gd^{III} and Yb^{III}-picrates are 10.86, 8.06 and 4.62 B.M. respectively.

The *f-f* electronic transitions of the lanthanides are found to be sharp and line-like and each may be characterised by the total angular quantum number (*J*). In the Pr^{III}, Nd^{III}, Sm^{III} and Dy^{III}-picrates we observed small shifts⁴ to lower frequencies were observed and which have all the bands reported in LnCl₃. The assignments of bands to different transi-

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL AND PHYSICAL DATA OF THE METAL PICRATES

Sl. no.	Compd.	Colour	Mol. wt ; Found/ (Calcd.)	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd.)				Molar cond.** cm ² Ω ⁻¹ mol ⁻¹	μ _{eff} (Corr.) B.M.	DP°/* CB°	EP/* Cc°
				Ln	H	C	N				
1.	La(Pic) ₃ .11H ₂ O	Golden yellow	1 018.48 (1 021.40)	13.2 (13.6)	2.61 (2.76)	20.78 (21.17)	12.08 (12.34)	64.0	0.18	292	340
2.	Pr(Pic) ₃ .11H ₂ O	Bright green	1 026.86 (1 032.84)	13.1 (13.8)	2.54 (2.76)	20.67 (21.13)	12.16 (12.32)	55.6	3.62	284	337
3.	Nd(Pic) ₃ .11H ₂ O	Yellowish green	1 022.41 (1 026.42)	14.2 (14.1)	2.63 (2.75)	20.98 (21.06)	12.24 (12.28)	58.4	3.52	288	344
4.	Sm(Pic) ₃ .11H ₂ O	Brownish yellow	1 018.32 (1 023.40)	14.2 (14.8)	2.74 (2.73)	21.41 (20.93)	11.46 (12.21)	53.2	1.70	286	340
5.	Dy(Pic) ₃ .8H ₂ O	Yellow	984.63 (990.95)	15.6 (16.4)	2.31 (2.24)	20.06 (21.82)	11.98 (12.72)	64.6	0.861	284	352
6.	Gd(Pic) ₃ .11H ₂ O	Dark yellow	1 026.42 (1 039.79)	14.8 (15.1)	2.54 (2.71)	20.02 (20.79)	12.16 (12.12)	60.8	8.06	286	344
7.	Yb(Pic) ₃ .8H ₂ O	Yellow	998.96 (1 001.49)	16.8 (17.3)	2.16 (2.21)	20.98 (21.59)	12.48 (12.59)	68.4	4.62	260	350

*Decomposition point (DP) and explosion point (EP) determined by DTA. ** In DMF (10⁻³ M).

TABLE 2—ELECTRONIC SPECTRAL (REFLECTANCE) DATA OF COMPOUNDS WITH 2,4,6-TRINITROPHENOL

Compd.	LnCl ₃ cm ⁻¹	Ln(Pic) ₃ .xH ₂ O cm ⁻¹	Band assignment	β	δ %	b _{1/2} × 10 ⁻³	Covalency angular overlap
Pr ^{III} (Picrate) ₃ .11H ₂ O	16 640	16 528	³ H ₄ → ¹ D ₂	0.993	0.705	5.92	8.1 × 10 ⁻³
	21 335	21 052	→ ³ P ₀	0.984	1.620	8.90	8.1 × 10 ⁻³
	24 780	24 390	→ ³ P ₁	0.984	1.620	8.90	8.1 × 10 ⁻³
Nd ^{III} (Picrate) ₃ .11H ₂ O	17 280	17 240	⁴ I _{9/2} → ⁴ G _{5/2}	0.998	0.204	3.20	1.0 × 10 ⁻³
	21 900	21 505	→ ⁴ G _{11/2}	0.982	1.833	9.50	9.1 × 10 ⁻³
	29 700	29 411	→ ² P _{1/2}	0.990	1.010	7.10	5.0 × 10 ⁻³
Sm ^{III} (Picrate) ₃ .11H ₂ O	21 600	20 250	⁶ H _{5/2} → ⁴ I _{13/2}	0.938	6.610	-167.40	31.99 × 10 ⁻³
	22 320	22 350	→ ⁶ P _{5/2}	1.001	0.134	-2.24	5.0 × 10 ⁻³
	24 940	24 540	→ ⁴ F _{11/2}	0.984	1.620	8.90	8.1 × 10 ⁻³
Dy ^{III} (Picrate) ₃ .8H ₂ O	21 050	21 276	⁶ H _{15/2} → ⁶ F _{7/2}	1.011	1.088	-7.42	5.5 × 10 ⁻³
	28 700	28 750	→ ⁶ F _{11/2}	1.002	0.20	-3.16	8.99 × 10 ⁻⁴

tions are based on comparison with the reflectance spectra of lanthanone(III) chloride. In the Pr^{III} picrate, a comparison of the calculated *J* levels from Pr^{III} chloride reveals three bands observed at 16 528, 21 052 and 24 390 cm⁻¹ respectively, which are assigned to energy levels ³H₄ → ¹D₂, ³H₄ → ³P₀ and ³H₄ → ³P₁ respectively. In the Nd^{III} picrate the hypersensitive band ⁴I_{9/2} → ⁴G_{5/2} is observed at 17 420 cm⁻¹ and the bands at 21 505 and 29 411 cm⁻¹ are assigned to ⁴I_{9/2} → ⁴G_{11/2} and ⁴I_{9/2} → ²P_{1/2} respectively. In the Sm^{III} picrate the *J* levels are calculated in comparison to Sm^{III} chloride host and three bands observed at 20 250, 22 350 and 24 520 cm⁻¹ are tentatively assigned to ⁶H_{5/2} → ⁴I_{13/2}, ⁶H_{5/2} → ⁶P_{5/2} and ⁶H_{5/2} → ⁴F_{11/2} respectively. In the Dy^{III} picrate the *J* levels are calculated in comparison to Dy^{III} chloride host and two bands observed at 21 050 and 28 000 cm⁻¹ are assigned to ⁶H_{15/2} → ⁶F_{7/2} and ⁶H_{15/2} → ⁶F_{11/2} respectively. The values of β and δ % and b_{1/2} calculated for the complexes are recorded in Table 2.

The observed spectra of picric acid in solid and solution phase (CHCl₃) show a marked difference in the position of OH group, clearly indicating⁵ the presence of intramolecular hydrogen bonding between OH group and NO₂ group present at *ortho*-position. A comparison of the nujol ir spectrum of lanthanone picrates with the solution spectra of picric acid

reveals that the bands due to the hydrogen-metal bond at 3 620–3 315 and 1 650–1 630 cm⁻¹, are absent in anhydrous metal picrates⁶ and they are attributed to ν_{OH} and δ_{OH} respectively of the water molecules present in the hydrated *f*-metal picrates. The sharp band observed at 880–650 cm⁻¹ is attributed to ρ_{H₂O} modes. The M–O stretching vibration in *f* metal picrates are observed at : La–O 290, Pr–O 305, Nd–O 310, Sm–O 340, Dy–O 340, Gd–O 345 and Yb–O 320 cm⁻¹. These parameters support the participation of phenolic oxygen in coordination of the lanthanone metals. Therefore, the results reveals high-spin octahedral stereochemistry of lanthanoid(III) ions :

Pharmacological studies : Picric acid, Pr^{III}, Nd^{III} and Sm^{III} picrates (0.2 mg/kg in water) were screened on blood pressure of albino rats. The Pr^{III} and Sm^{III} picrates exhibited biphasic response but picric acid and the Nd^{III} picrate exhibited hypotensive effect.

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